

Deliverable D5.1 Updating existing ontologies, and implementing in data resources

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Change Log

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

BIA	BioImage Archive
IDR	Image Data Resource
SSBD	A platform for Systems Science of Biological Dynamics
CL	Cell Ontology
CLO	Cell Line Ontology
CMPO	Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology
CSVW	CSV on the Web
ChEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest Ontology
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DOID	Human Disease Ontology
EDAM	EMBRACE Data and Methods ontology
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
GO	Gene Ontology
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
MONDO	Mondo Disease Ontology
MP	Mammalian Phenotype Ontology
NCBITaxon	NCBI organismal classification
OBI	Ontology for Biomedical Investigation
OBO	Open Biological and Biomedical Ontologies
ODK	Ontology Development Kit
OLS	Ontology Lookup Service
OME	Open Microscopy Environment
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images

RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
ROR	Research Organization Registry
RRID	Research Resource Identifier
UBERON	Uberon Multi-species Anatomy Ontology
UO	Units of Measurement Ontology
UniProt	Universal Protein Resource

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Executive Summary

A core goal of foundingGIDE was to support participating resources to harmonise their formal descriptions of image data using a shared vocabulary. Ontologies and controlled vocabularies provide much of that vocabulary. This deliverable reports on the work of WP5 to update the ontologies chosen as critical to the project, and to implement them within the participating data resources, so that submissions increasingly describe imaging data using agreed, resolvable terms.

The deliverable takes as its starting point the ontology set recommended in D2.1 (ontology landscaping and recommendations), and the per-component representation specified in D6.1. First it reports the return of the Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi) to active maintenance, now as a community effort under the FoundingGIDE project. New terms are being added using community-standard tooling, an open contribution process and continuity of its established identifiers. Second, it reports wider GIDE ontologies implementation in the participating resources. The BioImage Archive now uses FBbi identifiers internally within its RO-Crate-based metadata representation, and has published guidance enabling submitters to record ontology terms using its submission system. The corresponding implementation in SSBD, and guidance on future compatibility with the IDR, are reported in the respective sections. Preclinical imaging ontologies are addressed in D4.1 and are outside the scope of this deliverable. The longer-term sustainability of these maintenance arrangements is the subject of D5.2.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

A truly global image data ecosystem depends on the partner resources describing image data with a shared vocabulary, often supplied through Ontologies and controlled vocabularies. This allows a species, an imaging method, or a compound to be recorded once and then matched consistently across resources, enabling consistent search and discovery. This deliverable reports on the work carried out under WP5 to put that shared vocabulary into practice.

Specifically, the deliverable covers two things. First, it describes the updates made to the existing ontologies selected for the ecosystem, including the work undertaken to return the Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi) to active maintenance. Second, it describes how the selected ontologies have been implemented in the participating data resources, so that submissions increasingly make use of the agreed terms to describe imaging data. The BioImage Archive and SSBD are the two resources addressed in detail, with a note on future compatibility with the Image Data Resource (IDR).

1.2 Relationship to other deliverables and out of scope topics

This deliverable sits towards the implementation end of a chain of WP2, WP4, WP5 and WP6 outputs, and is best read alongside them rather than in isolation. It reports on the implementation of chosen ontologies and the updates required to them, in line with Task 5.2.

D2.1 provides the landscape analysis of existing ontologies and the recommendation of the imaging ontology set that this deliverable implements. One of the outputs of Task 5.1, D4.1 reports the recommended ontologies for preclinical image datasets and technologies, the domain deliberately set aside here. This is therefore noted only briefly here, in Section 3.5, as work that sits in that adjacent strand.

D6.1 (from WP6) sets out the overlaps and gaps between the metadata models of the BioImage Archive, IDR and SSBD, and proposes a set of harmonisation requirements together with a recommended representation for each metadata component; that representation underpins the implementation guidance described in Section 3.

Finally, the plan for keeping the chosen ontologies maintained beyond the lifetime of the project is the subject of D5.2, and is touched on here only insofar as the maintenance arrangements already established for FBbi point towards it (in Section 3.1).

2. Approach

2.1 The selected ontology set

The work reported here starts from the set of ontologies and controlled vocabularies recommended for the bioimage data management ecosystem in D2.1, following the landscape analysis carried out under WP2. That set was chosen for its coverage of the metadata components that matter most for cross-resource data harmonisation, search and reuse, for its grounding in openly maintained community resources wherever possible, and for its practicality of implementation in resources that already rely on lightweight controlled-vocabulary annotation.

D6.1 subsequently took that set and specified, component by component, how each should be represented in a harmonised metadata framework spanning the BioImage Archive, IDR and SSBD. The recommended representation is set out in D6.1. In summary, the selected vocabularies include FBbi for imaging methods, NCBITaxon for organism, the Cell Ontology and Cell Line Ontology for cell types and cell lines, Ensembl and UniProt for genes and proteins, ChEBI for compounds, the Experimental Factor Ontology for experimental conditions, UBERON for anatomy, the Units of Measurement Ontology for units, and MONDO with linkage to DOID and ICD-11 for disease, alongside identifier schemes such as ORCID, ROR and RRID for researchers, organisations and research resources. Readers are referred to D2.1 for the selection rationale and to D6.1 for the full representation table.

Of these, FBbi is distinctive in two respects that shaped the work of this work package. It is the vocabulary specific to the bioimaging domain rather than one borrowed from an adjacent field, so the project carries a particular responsibility for it; and, as noted below, it was the one element of the selected set that required intervention before it could be relied upon, as it was not actively maintained.

2.2 The case for taking over FBbi maintenance

FBbi occupies a position in the bioimaging ecosystem that no other ontology fills. It is the established vocabulary for sample preparation, visualisation and imaging methods, it is already used across all three of the partner resources, and it is recognised in the OBO Foundry. It is therefore the natural choice for the imaging-method component of the harmonised framework.

However, at commencement of the project, there were clear risks associated with reliance on FBbi. Maintenance had lapsed: the ontology had seen no substantive update for several years, and there was at that point no clear route by which new terms for emerging imaging modalities could be added. D6.1 noted this gap and raised the possibility of looking to alternative or complementary resources should the situation persist. Left unaddressed, that maintenance gap would have undercut the very interoperability the selected set was meant to support, since a vocabulary that cannot grow to describe new techniques steadily loses coverage as the field advances.

Given that risk, the project partners judged that the best long term response was to return FBbi to active maintenance. This is not to set FBbi against complementary resources: EDAM, for instance, continues to be used within the ecosystem for image analysis technique descriptions, a role distinct from the imaging-method vocabulary that FBbi provides. Reviving FBbi preserves the existing annotations and tooling that depend on it, keeps the bioimaging community's method vocabulary within a community-governed OBO ontology, and provides a route by which gaps in coverage can be closed as they are identified. The arrangements that put this into effect, and the early results of the term-addition work, are described in Section 3.1. The longer-term question of how this maintenance is sustained beyond the project is the subject of D5.2.

3. Implementation

3.1 Returning FBbi to active maintenance

The Biological Imaging Methods Ontology is now maintained, from 2026 onwards, as a joint community effort under the umbrella of the FoundingGIDE project, with primary maintenance carried out by German BioImaging. The source files are held in a public repository at <https://github.com/foundingGIDE/fbbi>, under a CC-BY-4.0 licence, and the ontology continues to be served through the established OBO Foundry channels: the stable release is available at the persistent identifier <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/fbbi.owl>, and terms can be browsed in the EBI Ontology Lookup Service. Maintaining continuity of these identifiers and access points was a deliberate choice, so that existing users of FBbi see no disruption as maintenance resumes.

The repository is built using the Ontology Development Kit, the standard tooling for OBO ontologies, which provides a reproducible release process and brings FBbi into line with the practices of the wider ontology community. Term addition and revision are handled openly. New terms and corrections can be requested through the repository's issue tracker (<https://github.com/foundingGIDE/fbbi/issues>). Requests may also be raised through the community's usual channels, including the image.sc forum, lowering the barrier for imaging scientists who are not regular users of version-control tooling. A release was made on 30 March 2026, and the work of adding terms, both by the maintainers and through community contributions, is ongoing rather than complete; the issue tracker holds a number of open term requests at the time of writing.

3.2 Implementation in the BioImage Archive

The BioImage Archive has approached implementation on two fronts: the internal representation of metadata within its newer infrastructure, and the guidance offered to submitters working with the current submission system.

Internal representation in the RO-Crate system

The BioImage Archive has adapted its systems so that the newer, RO-Crate-based representation of study metadata uses FBbi identifiers internally for the imaging-method component, rather than free-text descriptions. Recording the imaging method as a resolvable FBbi identifier within the

RO-Crate means that the value can be matched consistently against other resources that adopt the same vocabulary, and aligns the internal representation with the harmonisation requirements set out in D6.1. The structure of these RO-Crates, and the rules that a valid BIA RO-Crate must satisfy, are defined and checked by an openly developed validator (<https://github.com/BioImage-Archive/bia-ro-crate-validator>); within it, the file list that accompanies a submission is described using the CSVW vocabulary, which is what allows a file-list column header to be tied to a property drawn from a recommended ontology. This is the mechanism by which the submission-side guidance described below connects to the internal representation.

Guidance for the current submission system

Submissions to the BioImage Archive are described using a file list, a tabular file that provides key/value annotation for each file in a study component. The file list remains the primary route by which submitters supply per-file metadata, and so it is the natural place to encourage the use of ontology terms at the point of submission.

To that end, guidance has been prepared on how to use ontologies and controlled vocabularies within the existing format, as an addition to the published File List help. Submitters are asked to annotate only those attributes that vary between files within a component; values that are constant for a whole study belong in the study description captured through the submission web form, following REMBI, rather than in the file list. Each value is recorded as a single compact identifier in `prefix:accession` form, for example `NCBITaxon:9606`, with the prefix fixing the vocabulary from which the accession is drawn and following the Bioregistry and identifiers.org registries so that identifiers are unambiguous and resolvable. A human-readable label is treated as optional, since the identifier resolves to a single term, though submitters may keep a label in a separate descriptive column for their own convenience.

The guidance then maps the metadata attributes that commonly appear in file lists to the recommended vocabularies, drawing on the harmonisation requirements agreed in D6.1. The mapping is reproduced as Table 1. It distinguishes between OBO ontology terms that can be looked up in the Ontology Lookup Service and database accessions such as Ensembl genes or UniProt proteins that resolve in their own source databases rather than in OLS. The guidance closes with worked examples showing the single-identifier convention in the context of a compound-treatment component, a multi-species component and an antibody-target component, so that submitters can see the recommended form applied to realistic file lists.

Table 1: Recommended vocabularies by file-list attribute (preferred vocabulary; alternatives accepted shown in parentheses). Example accessions are illustrative; the exact term should be confirmed in OLS or the source database before use.

Suggested column	What it records	Recommended vocabulary	Example value	Notes
Imaging Method	The technique used to acquire the image	FBbi	FBbi:00000246	Often constant for a component, so usually belongs in the web form; use here only when it varies per file.
Organism	Species of the imaged sample	NCBITaxon	NCBITaxon:9606	Include only for multi-species components; otherwise enter once via the web form.
Cell Line	The cell line imaged	CLO (Cellosaurus RRID:CVCL_)	CLO:0009058	
Cell Type	The cell type, where not a named line	CL (Cell Ontology)	CL:0000057	
Gene	Gene under study or perturbed	Ensembl gene	ensembl:ENSG0000139618	Database accession, not an OBO term.
Protein	Protein associated with the file or channel	UniProt (EFO for broader entities)	uniprot:P38398	Database accession, not an OBO term.
Compound	Chemical or drug applied	ChEBI (PubChem)	CHEBI:28748	Pair with a units column for concentration.
Antibody	Antibody reagent used	RRID (antibody)	RRID:AB_2533106	RRID also issues identifiers for cell lines, organisms and tools.
Channel Content	- What a channel reports (label,	FBbi	FBbi:00000277	

Suggested column	What it records	Recommended vocabulary	Example value	Notes
	stain, fluorophore)			
Channel - Biological Entity	The biological entity a channel marks	UniProt (EFO)	uniprot:P38398	
Pathology / Disease	Disease or pathological state	MONDO (DOID, ICD-11; SNOMED CT)	MONDO:0007254	Prefer open vocabularies for international reuse.
Phenotype	Observed phenotype	CMPO (MP, HPO)	CMPO:0000077	HPO and MP for organism-specific phenotypes.
Organ / Anatomy	Anatomical structure or organ	UBERON	UBERON:0002107	
Experimental Condition	Experimental factor or assay condition	EFO (OBI)	EFO:0000001	
Units (e.g. Concentration, Time)	Unit of a numeric column	UO	UO:0000064	Put the number in its own column and the unit term here.

3.3 Implementation in SSBD

SSBD has adopted or already uses a broad set of the ontologies and controlled vocabularies selected for the foundingGIDE metadata harmonisation framework. These include NCBITaxon, FBbi, CL, CLO, ChEBI, UBERON, Ensembl, UniProt, GO, and UO. In addition, FBbi is used for protein tags and probes, while EFO is used to describe experimental or staining-related methods. SSBD also assigns MeSH terms to individual metadata components where appropriate, providing an additional layer of semantic annotation.

During the project, SSBD has also begun improving the representation of structured administrative metadata, particularly for funding information. Japanese funding bodies have been extracted from ROR (Research Organization Registry) and are being introduced into SSBD metadata descriptions to

support more consistent and machine-readable funding metadata. In parallel, SSBD has started to manage researcher and organisation identifiers using ORCID and ROR, respectively, strengthening the alignment of contributor and institutional metadata with internationally recognised identifier systems.

SSBD is also working on the use of RO-Crate to describe study-level metadata in a more interoperable and machine-readable form. As part of this effort, an API is being developed to enable the automatic generation of RO-Crate metadata from SSBD records. This work is intended to support future cross-resource discovery across BIA, IDR and SSBD by providing a common representation of study-level metadata.

For disease-related metadata, SSBD takes into account the licensing constraints associated with SNOMED CT in Japan, as highlighted in D6.1. At present, disease-related metadata are not extensively represented in SSBD. For future implementation, SSBD will preferentially consider open vocabularies such as MONDO and DOID, where appropriate, to support broader international reuse and interoperability.

In terms of implementation status, SSBD has refreshed the use interfaces of both SSBD:database and SSBD:repository. These updates have improved the visibility and usability of the metadata collected by the resource. Many metadata components are now searchable through the interface and are also displayed more clearly to users, enabling improved data discovery and access. Together, these developments improve metadata quality, discoverability, and interoperability within SSBD and provide a foundation for future integration with other bioimaging data resources.

3.4 Future compatibility with the IDR

The IDR already annotates against a substantial part of the selected set. Its published list of linked reference ontologies and databases recommends use of FBbi for imaging method, NCBI Taxonomy for organism, Ensembl and NCBI Gene for genes, UniProt for protein, the Experimental Factor Ontology for study, screen and protocol types, the Cellular Microscopy Phenotype Ontology for phenotype, PubChem for compounds and SNOMED CT for clinical and pathology terms. The selected set and the IDR's existing practice therefore overlap substantially.

The principal differences are those already identified in D6.1: the use of PubChem rather than ChEBI for compounds, and of SNOMED CT for clinical terms where the harmonised framework prefers open alternatives such as MONDO with linkage to DOID and ICD-11. The Image Data Resource, however, is not a beneficiary delivering implementation work within this task; the role here, provided by GerBI-OME, is to offer guidance on future compatibility with the IDR so that the selected ontologies can be accommodated as the resource evolves. Accordingly, no changes to the IDR are claimed under this deliverable.

3.5 Note on preclinical imaging ontologies

A range of ontologies addresses medical and preclinical imaging, covering biomedical imaging annotation, radiomics features and the interpretation of DICOM images, among others. The

investigation and evaluation of these, and the recommendation of a set for the preclinical domain, were carried out under Task 5.1 and reported in D4.1, and are not within the scope of the present deliverable. The implementation work reported here concerns the ontologies selected for the biological imaging resources participating in the project. Aligning the two domains, and accommodating preclinical metadata as partner datasets expand, is recognised in D6.1 as a direction for future work.

3.6 Summary

The work reported above establishes that the selected ontologies can be updated and put to use in the participating resources, and, in the case of FBbi, that a lapsed but essential ontology can be returned to active, community-governed maintenance.

4. References

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